

Acrylate based homo and copolymers as potential additives for lubricating oil

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Abstract : In the present work we prepared multifunctional additives for lubricating oil (lube oil) via the preparation of homopolymer of decyl acrylate (DA) and its copolymer with styrene and 1-decene. We studied the efficiency of the prepared compounds at different level of concentrations in lube oil as viscosity index improvers (VII), pour point depressants (PPD) and anti wear (AW) additives. Lube oil thickening property of the polymers, which is a direct measure of percent increase in the viscosity of the base stocks (lube oils) for addition of its unit amount of weight as well as an indicative of fuel economy, and the shear stability of the polymers in lube oil, which determines the stability of the polymer in field application (as an engine oil), has also been investigated and reported.

Keywords : Lubricating oil, homopolymer, copolymer, viscosity index (VI), kinematic viscosity (KV).

Introduction

Lubricating oils or lube oils also called base stocks are the basic building blocks of lubricants and are generally a mixture of high molecular weight hydrocarbons and an additive package. It reduces the friction and wear when introduced between two moving surfaces. They provide a protective film which allows for two touching surfaces to be separated and thus lessening the friction between them. Hence in internal combustion engines they are very essential for longer life of the engine. The major portion of the base stocks is a mixture of paraffinic hydrocarbons (> 85%) of different chain length. Naphthenic and aromatic hydrocarbons are also present in different ratios. At lower temperature the paraffinic portions of the lube oil forms wax crystal net work which inhibits their normal flow properties. Again, the change in viscosity of the base stocks with the change in temperature, low thermo-oxidative stability and tribological behavior etc. are the inherent problems associated with the base oils during its application. Thus, it is quite obvious that, natural petroleum based lubricants cannot satisfy all the requirements of modern engines. Hence a large number of functional additives are added to the lube oil to enhance the characteristic properties already present or to impart some new additional properties. Their amount varies from > 1% to

30% or more¹. The following types of lube oil additives are mainly used; viscosity modifier (VM) or viscosity index improver (VII)², pour point depressant (PPD)³, antioxidant⁴, antiwear and extreme pressure agent^{5,6}. Since multifunctional additives induce more than one of the above performances, research throughout the world is increasingly directed toward producing such kind of additives for lube oils. These additives are normally polymeric in nature, having long oil soluble hydrocarbon chain as non-polar portion and smaller hydrophilic polar head groups.

Viscosity index improvers (VII) also known as viscosity modifier (VM) are long chain, high molecular weight polymers used to resist the change of viscosity of the oil by increasing the relative viscosity of oil more at high temperatures than at low temperatures⁷⁻⁹. The performance of VMs is very often expressed in terms of Viscosity Index (VI), which is an arbitrary number¹⁰ that indicates the resistance of a lubricant to viscosity change with temperature. The performance of the VII depends on the behaviour of the polymer molecules in the oil, where the polymer solubility, molecular weight and resistant to shear degradation are determinant parameters¹¹. Shear stability of the VM is one of the important criteria that determine its suitability in a lubricant formulation. The loss of viscosity of a lubricant under shear can be of

two kinds, namely a temporary viscosity loss (TVL) and a permanent viscosity loss^{10,12} (PVL). The PVL values are more frequently expressed in terms of permanent shear stability index¹³ (PSSI).

A detailed study of the literature indicated that only a few investigations have so far been carried out on the effects of lubricant compositional parameters such as polymer type, polymer concentration, base oil viscosity, etc. on the additive performance of multigrade lubricants.

Keeping these views in mind and as a part of our ongoing studies on the development of multifunctional additives for lube oil¹⁴, studies were undertaken in this area to investigate the VI, PPD, AW, shear stabilities, and thickening (THK) properties of the homopolymer of DA (P1) and its copolymer with styrene (P2) and 1-decene (P3) when doped in lube oil. The observations in each case have been correlated towards arriving at possible generalization on this effect for lube oils.

Results and discussion

TGA analysis : The analysis (Table 1) reveals that the DA homopolymer are thermally less stable than its copolymer with styrene which in turn less stable than DA copolymer with 1-decene.

Table 1. Thermogravimetric analysis, $[\eta]_h^a$ and $[M_h]^b$ data of the prepared sample

Sample	Decomp. temp.	PWL	$[\eta]_h^a$	$[M_h]^b$
P-1	250/340	23/86	2.354	8315
P-2	300/400	45/84	1.851	5396
P-3	320/430	50/83	1.532	4211

^aIntrinsic viscosity. ^bViscometric molecular weight of polymer.

Performance evaluation of the additive doped lube oil as PPD : Results (Fig. 1) indicate that the PPD (pour point depressant) properties of different polymer in lube oil increases with increasing concentration of the additive in the solution and at a particular concentration it increases from 1-decene to styrene copolymer and to DA homopolymer (Fig. 1) which is evidently due to increasing molecular weight (Table 1) of the above mentioned polymers.

Performance evaluation of the additive doped lube oil as VII : The study (Table 2) shows that the VI value for DA polymer is greater than DA+styrene and DA+1-

Fig. 1. Comparison of pour point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) among P-1, P-2 and P-3 polymers of different concentrations (mass fractions) in base oil.

decene copolymer. Thus, the VII (viscosity index improver) properties of the homopolymer of DA are better than its DA+styrene and DA+1-decene copolymer.

Evaluation of AW performance of the additive doped lube oil : The study (Table 2) shows that the AW properties in terms of WSD in cm for DA+styrene copolymer are always greater than DA+1-decene copolymer as well as the homopolymer. This may be because of the presence of aromatic moiety in the copolymer. There is always a gradual increase of AW properties with the concentration (up to a certain limit) of the additive in the lube oil-polymer blends.

Table 2. VI values and AW properties (WSD data) of the additives doped in base oil

Mass fraction of the additive (x_2)	VI			AW (WSD in cm at 196 N weld load)		
	P-1	P-2	P-3	P-1	P-2	P-3
0.000	-	-	-	1.116	1.116	1.116
0.010	71.06	69.30	68.01	1.106	1.083	1.089
0.020	79.18	77.60	76.34	1.098	1.067	1.078
0.030	93.69	92.27	91.21	1.065	1.032	1.054
0.040	100.47	97.87	97.87	1.066	1.022	1.045
0.050	110.50	109.29	108.65	1.063	1.021	1.042

PSSI and PVL analysis : Data (Figs. 2 and 3) showed that PSSI and PVL values are greater for homo polymer of DA than its styrene and 1-decene copolymer. It indicates less shear stability of DA homo polymer than both

Fig. 2. Comparison of PSSI among P-1, P-2 and P-3 polymers of different concentrations (mass fractions) in base oil.

Fig. 3. Comparison of PVL among P-1, P-2 and P-3 polymers of different concentrations (mass fractions) in base oil.

of its styrene and 1-decene copolymer. It also denotes increase of PSSI values with increase in concentration of all above mentioned polymers in base oil which signify the gradual loss in shear stability. The prediction is the direct reflection¹⁵ of the molecular weight values of the polymers as shown in Table 1. High molecular weight of the polymer results in greater hydrodynamic volume. Higher molecular mass and lower molecular association with the base oil¹⁶ increases the VII properties but at the same time these increases PSSI and PVL values as well.

The intrinsic viscosity data (Table 1) also imply the

higher molecular size of homopolymer than copolymer. This phenomenon is expected to play a significant role in determining shear stability of the base oil-polymer blend.

Thickening property analysis : The study also indicated that there is no correlation of oil thickening properties (THK) among the homo and copolymers as well as among the different concentrations of the same polymer at 313 K and 373 K (Figs. 4 and 5). The oil thickening properties of the polymer are concordance with the result of our earlier observations¹⁷.

Fig. 4. Comparison of THK at 313 K among P-1, P-2 and P-3 polymers of different concentrations (mass fractions) in base oil.

Fig. 5. Comparison of THK at 373 K among P-1, P-2 and P-3 polymers of different concentrations (mass fractions) in base oil.

Experimental

Esterification and polymerization : Esterification of acrylic acid with decyl alcohols, purification of the prepared esters and subsequent polymerization (homo and copolymerization with styrene and 1-decene) were carried out following the procedure as reported earlier publications¹⁸.

Materials :

Toluene, hydroquinone and H₂SO₄ were purchased from Merck Specialities Pvt. Ltd., acrylic acid (stabilised with 0.02% hydroquinone monomethylether), decyl alcohol from Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., hexane from SD Fine Chem. Ltd., styrene and 1-decene from Across Organics and methanol was purchased from Thomas Baker (Chemicals) Pvt. Ltd. and were used as they obtained without further purification. Benzoyl peroxide (BZP), obtained from LOBA chemicals, was recrystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH mixture before use. Base oils were collected from IOCL, Dhakuria, Kolkata, West Bengal, India.

Measurements :

Spectroscopic measurement : Shimadzu FT-IR 8300 spectrophotometer was used to record the IR spectra of the samples using KBr cells (0.1 mm) at room temperature. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ in a 300 MHz Bruker Avance FT-NMR spectrometer using 5 mm BBO probe. Tetramethylsilane (TMS) was used as the reference material.

Determination of intrinsic viscosity and viscometric molecular weight of the polymers : Intrinsic viscosity and viscometric molecular weight (Table 1) were determined by using the experimental viscosity of the polymer solutions in Huggins and Mark Houwink-Sukurda equation respectively¹⁹.

TGA determination : The thermograms in air were obtained on a Mettler TA-3000 system, at a heating rate of 10 K min⁻¹.

Pour point determination : The pour point of the prepared polymers in base oils was tested according to the ASTM D97-09 method on a Cloud and Pour Point Tester model WIL-471 (India).

Viscosity index determination : Kinematic viscosity (KV) of the polymers was determined separately at 40 °C

and 100 °C by counting the time of flow of polymer solution in base oil using viscometer apparatus and measuring the density of it. According to ASTM D-7042 method and also by using the method of viscosity index calculation as reported in literature⁷, the viscosity index of each polymer solution was determined.

Shear stability determination : Shear stability of the solutions of polymers with varying concentrations was determined in lube oil. Tests and calculation were conducted as per ASTM D-3945 and ASTM 6022 method.

Anti wear (AW) properties : The AW properties were evaluated by four ball wear test apparatus (FBWT) according to ASTM D 4172-94 method applying weld load, 196 N at 75 °C for 30 min. The rotating speed of the ring was 1200 rpm. The wear scar diameter, show anti wear properties of the oils, was measured adding polymers at different concentration levels.

Conclusions

- (i) Thermal stability of the polymer doped base oil decreases with increasing molecular weight of the polymer. The data also indicates that the 1-decene copolymer can be used safely up to 300 °C whereas the styrene copolymer may be used upto a temperature around 280 °C, which is always greater than the homopolymer.
- (ii) PPD properties of the polymer blended lube oil solution increases with increasing polymer concentration.
- (iii) VI as well as THK properties of the homopolymer doped base oil are better than its styrene copolymer which in turn superior to DA + 1-decene copolymer doped base oil.
- (iv) AW properties of the polymer blended lube oil increases with increasing polymer concentration. Copolymers are better than the homopolymer and the DA-styrene doped base oil found to be the best.
- (v) Shear stability of the lube oil-copolymer blend is always better than the homopolymer.
- (vi) Irrespective of the nature of the polymers (homo or copolymer) there is a gradual decrease in shear stability with the increase in concentration of the polymers in the base oils used for the study.

- (vii) Correlation of oil thickening properties among the homo and copolymers as well as among the different concentrations of the same polymer cannot be made.

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